

Effect Of Cross Age Tutoring Strategy On Interest And Academic Achievement Of Senior Secondary School Students In Trigonometry In Abuja, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effect of cross-age tutoring strategy on students' academic achievement and interest in trigonometry among senior secondary school students in Abuja, Nigeria. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design, specifically the pre-test and post-test control group design. The population of the study was 10,936 SS II students from all public senior secondary schools in the Federal Capital Territory, a sample of 162 students was selected from two schools using simple random and purposive sampling techniques. Two instruments were used for data collection: the Trigonometry Achievement Test (TAT) and the Trigonometry Interest Scale (TIS). The reliability coefficients of the instruments were 0.87 and 0.86 respectively. The experimental group was taught using cross-age tutoring strategy, whereas the control group were taught with conventional lecture method. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and Mann Whitney U test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The finding of the study revealed that students taught trigonometry using cross-age tutoring strategy had higher mean achievement and interest scores than their counterparts taught using the conventional method. The study concluded that cross-age tutoring enhances students' academic performance and promotes positive interest in mathematics learning. It was recommended that mathematics teachers should employ cross-age tutoring strategy in classroom instruction to improve students' achievement and interest, and that training workshops should be organized to familiarize teachers with the technique.

Keywords: Cross-age tutoring, Academic achievement, Students' interest, Trigonometry, Instructional strategy, Mathematics education

INTRODUCTION

Education has been one of the most effective tools of ensuring economic growth and sustainable development of a country over the long term. Education helps societies to pass their knowledge, skills and values, which enable people to cope with the changing social and technological environment. In the modern fast-paced world, which is highly scientific and technologically developed, quality education can hardly be over-emphasized. Governments and teachers should thus see to it that educational systems especially in science and technology related courses are kept up to date with the current needs in the world and the country. In the list of

other fields that contribute to scientific and technological advances, mathematics is one of the pillars, and it is the basis of scientific innovations in artificial intelligence, climate modeling, data analysis, space exploration, and medical technology (Federal Ministry of Education, 2013; Akinosa, 2022).

Mathematics is accepted universally as the root of scientific and technological advancement as it concerns the reasoning, measurement, and problem-solving (Suleiman and Hammed, 2019). This is because of its relevance to the national development, economic growth, and technological advancement which has led to its being a mandatory subject in all levels of education in Nigeria. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) pointed out that the goals of mathematics education include the establishment of a strong base in logical thinking, computational skills, creativity, and problem-solving and development of positive attitudes towards the subject. In spite of this acknowledged significance, consistent underachievement in mathematics in Nigeria among secondary school students is reflected in consistent accounts in WAEC Chief Examiners Reports (2013- 2023) of systemic issues, including inefficient instructional practices, abstractness in the curriculum content, and low student involvement (Ezeugo and Agwagah, 2020).

Trigonometry is one of the critical subjects in secondary school mathematics that dwells on angles and sides of triangles. In astronomy, navigation, architecture, and engineering, trigonometry has become fundamental, and it is used to reason about space and measure it (Olatunde, 2021). In addition to the practical uses of trigonometry, it increases the level of analytical and logical thinking among the students. Nevertheless, studies have revealed that a significant number of students are having problems with the learning of trigonometric concepts because of their abstract nature and the prevalence of the teacher-centred approach to learning, including the lecture approach, which does not encourage active learning (Adeniji, 2020; Awofala and Agbolade, 2023). These issues necessitate the implementation of new learning methods that are student centred and make mathematical learning a more interactive, practical and meaningful in the experiences of the students.

Instructional strategies play a pivotal role in shaping students' achievement and retention of mathematical concepts. Although the lecture method remains the most commonly used approach in teaching mathematics across Nigerian secondary schools, research shows it is often teacher-centred and encourages passive learning with minimal student interaction (Shuaibu, Ibrahim, & Ezekiel, 2024). In contrast, interactive and student-centred strategies have been found to significantly enhance students' achievement and engagement. For instance, Oribhabor (2020) reported that students taught with activity-based learning strategies performed better in mathematics than those taught using the conventional lecture method. Similarly, peer tutoring has been shown to improve students' understanding and achievement in mathematics, as demonstrated by Awofala and Agbolade (2023) in their study among senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria.

A related strategy, cross-age tutoring, involves pairing older students as tutors with younger learners to promote peer-assisted learning. Studies have revealed that cross-age tutoring enhances academic achievement, reinforces tutors' mastery of subject matter, and fosters positive attitudes toward learning (Haynes & Brendle, 2019; Demir & Kilic, 2023). Through such cooperative interactions between students of different ages and abilities, both cognitive and affective development are promoted, making cross-age tutoring a promising instructional strategy for teaching complex mathematical topics such as trigonometry.

The interest as one of the main affective variables is also a core component of learning, along with the instructional strategies. Once the student develops interest in an academic subject, it provides them with a chance of intense engagement, endurance, and achievement in academic work (Obodo, 2020; Lung, 2021). Therefore, teachers are supposed to employ instructional strategies that will ensure that the students are inquisitive enough to captivate their attention and create an urge to learn.

As the students are currently achieving low in trigonometry, the deficiency in the current teaching practices involving lectures and the possible effectiveness of interactive learning practices such as cross-age tutoring, there is urgent need to identify alternative teaching practices that can help in increasing the academic performance and the interest of the students. Thus, the article examined the impacts of cross age tutoring strategy on the achievement and the interest of trigonometry among the senior secondary school students in Abuja, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The trend of low achievement of students in mathematics has remained a thorn in the flesh of mathematics educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers. Various teaching methods have been developed and applied over the years to curb the issue of poor performance in mathematics. Nevertheless, even after such attempts, the academic performance by the students in the subject is still disappointingly low. This means that strategies employed by the teachers might not be effective in enhancing meaningful learning and interest and achievement in mathematics by the students.

Even though the researchers have argued on the various student-centred methods of teaching such as cross age tutoring, guided inquiry and scaffolding strategies, it appears that the lecture style still consumes the classrooms of most Nigerian schools. It is teacher centered because most of the lecture method is likely to make the students limited to a small involvement, creativity, imagination and problem solving. Information is thus, just passed to the learner rather than him being an active participant in development of his own interpretation of mathematical concepts.

This has caused a lot of worry among the mathematics teachers who are constantly exploring on how and when they can embrace good teaching and learning methods that can enable them meet the goals of math education in Nigeria. Students achieve unsatisfactorily when it comes to mathematics, particularly in such areas as trigonometry, regardless of the introduction of various innovative teaching strategies. The recurrent poor performance provokes serious questions: Could a shift in the instructional strategy help to increase the performance and interest of students to mathematics? Will cross-age tutoring strategy be more effective in improving the achievement and interest of students when compared to the standard lecture?

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of cross age tutoring strategy on interest and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in trigonometry in Abuja, Nigeria Specifically the study sought to determine;

1. The effect of cross age tutoring strategy and lecture method on students' academic achievement in trigonometry.
2. The effect of cross age tutoring strategy and lecture method on students' interest on trigonometry.

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the study

1. What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught trigonometry with cross age tutoring strategy and those taught with lecture method?
2. What is the difference between the mean interest scores of students' taught trigonometry with cross age tutoring strategy and those taught with lecture method

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of students' taught trigonometry with cross age tutoring strategy and those taught with lecture method

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the interest of students' taught trigonometry with cross age strategy and those taught with lecture method.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study was quasi-experimental design of the pre-test, post-test control group. It was a pretest posttest control group factorial design of 2x2x2 factorial. The design consisted of two instructional groups cross age tutoring and conventional groups, gender at two levels (male and female). Two intact classes labelled A and B were used for the study in each of the schools selected. Intact class A served as the experimental group using the cross age tutoring strategy while intact class B served as the control group using the conventional method.

The population of the study was 10, 936 SS II students in all public senior secondary schools in the six Area Councils in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The sample size of 162 SS II students was drawn from two

Secondary Schools in Kuje. Simple random Sampling and purposive Sampling was adopted in selecting the sample size and intact classes.

Instrumentation

The instrument used for obtaining data for this study was Trigonometry Achievement Test (TAT) which contained 40 items adopted from past WAEC questions and Trigonometry Interest Scale (TIS). The TAT instrument consists of 40 multiple-choice objective test items with four options (A–D) where only one answer is correct while the other three are distracters, developed to assess the achievement of both the experimental and control groups. Each item has one mark, making 40 marks in total. The Mathematics topics from which TAT items were drawn was the Trigonometry topic of SS II. The instrument was adopted from West African Examination past question papers from 2013–2023 in Mathematics. The questions were spread in line with the cognitive domain of Bloom’s taxonomy of educational objectives. The Trigonometry Interest Scale was designed by the researcher to determine the interest of students.

Trigonometry Achievement Test (TAT) was adopted from WAEC past questions; hence, face validity was assured. To ensure validity of TIS, the instruments were subjected to thorough scrutiny by two experts in the Faculty of Education, University of Abuja, and one secondary school Mathematics teacher. Suggestions made were incorporated into the final version of the instrument used in the study. In order to determine the reliability of the research instruments, a pilot testing was carried out in one intact Mathematics class of SS II. Students were trial-tested, scripts marked, and scores recorded. Data collected were subjected to statistical analysis, and the reliability coefficient (r) level of the test instruments TAT and TIS to be used for the study was determined. Hence, the reliability coefficient of 0.87 and 0.86 for TAT and TIS respectively was obtained using Cronbach Alpha reliability to determine the internal consistency of the instruments.

Data Collection Procedure

The data were collected using Trigonometry Achievement Test (TAT) and Trigonometry Interest Scale (TIS). The researcher employed the assistance of a research assistant from each school. The Mathematics teachers were trained for one week as research assistants for both the experimental and control groups. Lesson plans and materials were given to them. The experimental group was taught using cross age tutoring strategy while the control group was taught using the conventional method. The researcher administered the pretest to both the experimental and control groups to ascertain their entry behavior. In the pretest, the TAT and TIS were administered to the groups. Multiple-choice question sheets were provided, and the researcher marked the sheets to obtain students’ scores before the treatment. This provided baseline data on students’ interest and achievement in Trigonometry.

After the pretest, the train research assistant taught the students in experimental and control group which lasted for 5 weeks, thereafter, Post-test was administered in week six after the treatment. The TAT items were reshuffle and administered to the students as post-test. This was done by the researcher in collaboration with the Mathematics teachers in each school. The respondents were left to work independently, and their responses were collected immediately. The researcher marked the sheets of the TAT and TIS to obtain students’ scores after the treatment. Thereafter, the researcher administered the Trigonometry Interest Scale (TIS) for both experimental and control group students to determine their interest in the topic.

Method of Data Analysis

The Data collected from pretest and posttest using descriptive statistics of Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while inferential statistics of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and Mann Whitney U test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The rule is that any hypothesis greater than $p > 0.05$ was accepted and any hypothesis less than $p < 0.05$ was rejected.

RESULTS

The results of this study are presented based on research questions raised and the hypotheses formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

Research Question One: *What is the difference between mean score of students taught trigonometry with cross age tutoring strategy and those taught with conventional method?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of academic achievement Scores of Students Taught Trigonometry Using Cross Age Tutoring Strategy and Those Taught Using the conventional Method

Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean difference
Cross Age Tutoring	75	32.39	6.28	13.71
Conventional Method	87	18.68	8.73	

Table 1: shows the mean and standard deviation of students in cross age tutoring strategy and conventional method groups with respect to their achievement scores in trigonometry. From the results obtained, cross age tutoring strategy group had a mean achievement score of 32.39 with a standard deviation of 6.28 while the conventional method group had a mean achievement score of 18.68 with a standard deviation of 8.73. Therefore, the mean difference in achievement scores between cross age tutoring strategy and conventional method groups is 0.39 in favour of students in cross age tutoring strategy group.

Research Question Two: *What is the different between the mean interest score of students taught trigonometry with cross age tutoring strategy and those taught with conventional method?*

Mean and Standard Deviation of Interest Rating Scores of Students Taught Trigonometry Using Cross Age Tutoring Strategy and Those Taught Using the conventional Method.

Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean difference
Cross Age Tutoring	75	3.06	0.19	0.39
conventional Method	87	2.67	0.33	

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of students in cross age tutoring strategy and conventional method g with respect to their interest rating scores in trigonometry. From the results obtained, cross age tutoring strategy group mean interest rating score of 3.06 with a standard deviation of 0.19 while the conventional method group had a interest rating score of 2.67 with a standard deviation of 0.33. Therefore, the mean difference in interest rating s between cross age tutoring strategy and conventional method groups is 0.39 in favour of students in cross age tut strategy group.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students’ taught trigonometry with cross age strategy and those taught with conventional method

Table 3: ANCOVA Results of Mean Achievement Scores of Students Taught trigonometry with cross age tut strategy and those taught with conventional method

Source	Type III Sum of Square: Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	7569.625 ^a 4	1892.406	31.379	0.000
Intercept	27870.432 1	27870.432	462.139	0.000
Pretest	0.029 1	0.029	0.000	0.983
Gender	0.366 1	0.366	0.006	0.938
Group	7540.321 1	7540.321	125.031	0.000
Gender * Group	0.134 1	0.134	0.002	0.963
Error	9468.276 157	60.307		
Total	118488.000 162			
Corrected Total	17037.901 161			

Dependent Variable: Achievement a. R Squared = .444 (Adjusted R Squared = .430)

Table 3 shows the ANCOVA result of achievement scores of students taught trigonometry with cross age tutoring strategy and those taught with conventional method. From the result, there is significant difference in the achievement scores of students taught trigonometry with cross age tutoring strategy and those taught with conventional method at 0.05 level of significance $F(1, 161) = 125.031$, $P(0.000)$ is less than 0.05. Therefore, hypothesis one is rejected as it can be concluded that cross age tutoring strategy of teaching the experimental group had significant impact on the achievement scores of the students in trigonometry as compared to those taught with conventional method.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the interest of students' taught trigonometry with cross age tutoring strategy and those taught with conventional method.

Table 4: Summary of Mann Whitney Results of Interest Rating of Students Taught Trigonometry with Cross Age Tutorial Strategy (CATS) and Those Taught with conventional Method (CM)

Group	N	Mean Ran	Sum of Rank	Mann Whitney U	Z	<u>Sig@0.05</u>	Remark
CATS	75	110.26	8269.50	1105.500	7.265	0.000	Significant
LM	87	56.71	4933.50				

From Table 4 results of the Mann Whitney test shows that the computed mean interest rank scores are 110.26 and 56.71 by CATS and CM groups respectively. The computed sum of ranks scores is 8269.50 and 4933.50 by CATS and CM groups respectively. The computed Mann Whitney U value of 1105.500 is higher than the 7.265 Z scores. The computed p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the mean interest development students in CATS group is significantly higher than that developed by students in CM group. Consequently, hypothesis three is hereby rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study revealed that students taught trigonometry with cross age tutoring strategy had higher achievement and interest than those taught with conventional method. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Yahya (2024), Salihu (2019) who reported that cross age tutoring with its instructional events is effective in bringing about improvement in classroom instruction. Similarly, the finding supports the findings of Afolabi and Falade (2023) who stated that cross age tutoring was more effective regarding improving learners' content knowledge in mathematics and interest than the conventional method. The finding also supports the studies of Kwetu (2024), Akpokiniovu and Akudolu (2023), who revealed that cross age tutoring was superior to conventional teaching method on learners understanding and interest in trigonometry.

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions were made based on the findings of the study; cross age tutoring has helped in improving the academic achievement, and interest of senior secondary school mathematics students. Therefore, it is a viable instructional strategy that the potential of enhancing students' academic achievement and interest trigonometry.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the finding, it is recommended that;

1. Teachers should expose mathematics students to Cross age tutoring strategy because it enhanced students' academic achievement in trigonometry
2. Mathematics teachers should be trained and retrained on how to utilize Cross age tutoring strategy since the method was found to be effective in enhancing students' academic interest in trigonometry

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